

CURRENT SCIENCE

Historical Development of Secularism

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Abstract

A political philosophy known as secularism holds that all faiths should be treated on an equal footing and that the state should not endorse any faith. Throughout the course of human history, the evolution of secularism has been impacted by the political, social, and cultural conditions that prevailed in a variety of countries. On the other hand, in general, secularism is a notion that arose in the modern period and is the product of the enlightenment movement that took place in Europe. With the fall of the Roman Empire, it was the religion of Christianity that was responsible for the first recorded instance of the adoption of the concept of secularism. Throughout the Middle Ages, it was usual for countries in Europe to adopt Christianity as their official state religion. Nonetheless, throughout this time there were several different discussions on the topic of secularism. The Reformation in the 16th century is credited with being the beginning of the contemporary secularist movement. The tensions between Catholicism and Protestantism manifested themselves more clearly following the propagation of the concept that religious practice and governmental authority were to be kept distinct, as well as throughout the course of the French Revolution, which took place simultaneously.

CURRENT SCIENCE

The French Revolution was a significant step toward the total separation of religion and governmental affairs as well as the guarantee of religious freedom. [Citation needed] [Citation needed] [Citation needed] The Papal State was eliminated because of the Revolution, and the possessions of the churches were nationalized. After the revolution, the idea of secularism started to become more widespread throughout Europe. During the 20th century, several nations came to accept secularism as their official ideology. It was also acknowledged as an important basic concept for the preservation of other human rights, such as the freedom of religion and the freedom of speech. This was done since secularism is a fundamental value. In today's world, the idea of secularism is incorporated into the founding documents of a significant number of states, as well as being acknowledged by international law.

Keywords: *State, Religion, Christianity, Middle Ages, French Revolution.*

Introduction

During history, several debates and discussions have arisen because of the cohabitation of two significant institutions, namely religion and politics. Conflicts have occasionally broken out because of several factors, most notably the role of religion in everyday life and the struggle to maintain political authority over religious institutions. On the other hand, during the modern era, particularly in conjunction with the enlightenment movement, the concept of maintaining a wall of separation between religion and politics was proposed. The evolution of the idea of secularism was significantly influenced by this concept, which played a crucial role. The idea of secularism refers to the separation of religion and the activities of the state, as well as the ability of the state to operate independently of any religion or belief. In addition to ensuring that individuals have the freedom to believe and worship as they see fit, secularism also works to ensure that people of diverse religions and beliefs are afforded the same legal protections. In addition to its significance in relation to democracy and the protection of human rights, secularism is an essential value. First developed in the Western culture, the idea of secularism eventually made its way to various regions of the globe. The concept of secularism is one that has been embraced by a great number of nations, including Turkey, and included into the founding documents of those nations. Despite this, discussions are still going on concerning the appropriateness of secularism and how successful it is in practice.

CURRENT SCIENCE

The model of secularism is an idea that envisions the separation of state and religion and that the state should not be linked with any religious institution. This concept is referred to as secularism. The goal of secularism is to defend the freedom of religion and to promote religious tolerance. As a result, secularism makes it possible for both the state and religious institutions to function without interference. Strict adherence to the principles of secularism not only shields public institutions from the influence of religious dogma, but also ensures that governments are free to reject or ignore religious convictions altogether. A model that was formed in the Western world with the formation of modern nation-states, secularism is implemented in many nations today. Secularism was developed in the Western world.

The concept of secularism has evolved in a variety of diverse ways across the countries that make up Europe. In England, for instance, the Anglican Church is recognized as the "official state church," but the practice of other religions is not restricted in any way. In contrast, the state of Germany has established a paradigm in which multiple religions are regarded as equal, rather than the official adoption of a single religion by the state. This approach may be found in Germany. In a similar vein, in Italy, although there is a separation of church and state, the Catholic Church yet maintains a significant amount of power. Because of this, the idea of secularism is understood and practiced in a variety of ways around the world.

The purpose of this research is to investigate the religion-state relations as well as the evolution of the concept of secularism, to trace the historical progression of the phenomenon of secularism, and to contribute to the existing body of literature in political science regarding this topic.

Working Methods/Method

Secularism and Its Different Meanings

The term "secularism" comes from the Latin word "laicus," which means "belonging to the people" or "outside the church." The English word "secularism" is derived from this word. Throughout the Medieval Ages, anyone who questioned the laws of the Catholic Church, such as those that required a priest to go to a given spot or to wear a certain attire to sustain a holy life, were referred to as heretics. This word came into usage in the Middle Ages (Berkes , 2003, pp. 16-17). A type of governance is said to be secular if the religious authority is independent from the political authority or if it has a different structure from the political power. According to Hocagolu (2014), p. 132, the term "secularism" refers to a system in which "religion and state

CURRENT SCIENCE

issues are separated from one another, no religion is embraced by the state, and everyone is allowed to practice their faith freely."

The idea of secularism is multifaceted and can be interpreted in a variety of ways depending on the field of study. The idea of secularism can be approached in a variety of ways within several fields of study, including law, political science, sociology, and philosophy. Because of this, there is no one agreed-upon definition of secularism, and several perspectives and debates continue to be held on it (Arabacı, 2003, page 12). The idea of secularism, which can have several interpretations according on the cultural, historical, political, and social context in which it is discussed, generates a great deal of controversy. It is possible for secularism to signify both the separation of religion and state and the absence of any religious belief on the part of the state when it is used in this context. In addition, the concept of secularism may be found as a guiding legal principle in the constitutions of certain nations, whereas in others, this concept has not been completely implemented in everyday life. Because of this, a variety of viewpoints and arguments on the notion of secularism, as well as its meaning and applications, continue to take place (Gunn , 2014, pp. 108-109).

The definition of secularism according to the Turkish Language Association is "an understanding that states that the state does not belong to any religion or sect, that everyone can choose any religion or belief, that they cannot be pressured, that religious affairs will be carried out within the framework of personal freedoms and that the state will remain impartial in these matters" (Türce Sozlük, 1998, p. 1449). This is according to the Turkish Language Association.

In his definition, Vaner places an emphasis on the fact that secularism refers to a political system that respects all faiths, fosters tolerance, and forbids the use of a particular faith as a tool for dominance. It also brings to light the fact that assuming authority by one is lonesome is forbidden by the majority. In the framework of this discussion, the link between secularism and democracy centers on the question of how the secularist values of tolerance and plurality are operationalized in democratic societies. It is possible to view secularism as the guardian of democracy since it enables individuals to freely live their lives and express their beliefs while at the same time embracing all faiths and disbeliefs equally (Vaner, 2001, p. 170).

Not only does the idea of secularism refer to maintaining a wall of separation between church and state, but it also entails adhering to several other fundamental precepts. These ideas include liberty, equality, tolerance, pluralism, and democratic governance, among others. In line with

CURRENT SCIENCE

these values, a secular state will protect the freedom of religion, opinion, and expression of all its people, will accept religious and cultural diversity, and will treat all its residents the same. One of the foundational tenets of a democratic society is the concept of secularism, which, when it is practiced in line with these tenets, makes it possible for individuals of many religious views, cultural backgrounds, and ways of life to coexist peacefully (Ruiz , 2007, p. 23). In secularism, the people themselves are seen to be the source of sovereignty, rather than the judicial system, religious authority, or divine sources, all of which are rejected by secularists as potential sources of sovereignty. Religion and state are kept apart in a secular state, which is characterized by a separated organizational structure. Under this system, the state acknowledges and respects all faiths and believes equally, guarantees the right to practice one's religion or belief, but at the same time, it does not accept any religious belief as part of its official state policy. Because of this, the notion of the separation of church and state is frequently linked with the concept of secularism.

It is mentioned in Başgil's definition of secularism that religion should have a certain level of autonomy in relation to the state. This contrasts with the concept of secularism, which refers to the neutrality of the state toward religious views. In addition, the norms that are defined by religion should not be the basis for the creation of laws in a secular state; rather, laws should be crafted in accordance with the requirements of the society and the reality of life (Başgil, 2017, p. 168). Various historical and cultural circumstances in various nations have had varying degrees of influence on the implementation of secularism, which has resulted in the development of a variety of distinct types of secularism. For instance, the idea of secularism in Turkey is linked to Atatürk's modernization program and the guiding principle behind the establishment of the Turkish Republic; as a result, it possesses traits that are distinct from those of the French tradition. Because of this, secularism may take on a variety of meanings and looks depending on the historical context and the society in which it is practiced (Arman, 2003, pp. 207-209).

Historical Development of Secularism

In terms of the political power struggle between church and state, the idea of secularism extends back considerably further than the French Revolution and the Enlightenment Period, when viewed in terms of its current meaning, the notion of secularism got its current meaning during those periods. This battle was reflected in the relationships that existed between the church and states in Europe during the Middle Ages. The fight for power between the church and the state

CURRENT SCIENCE

became even more intense throughout the 16th century, particularly because of the Reformation movement. Although it lessened the political influence of the church, the Protestant Reformation brought to light the critical need of religious liberty and conscience protection within the Christian faith. As a result of this process, the concept that the relationship that now exists between the church and the state need to be rethought has arisen. In this sense, the idea of secularism is something that emerged because of a battle that lasted for half a millennium and was founded on a profoundly intellectual grounding (Ilgaz, 2005, pp. 15-16).

From the 5th century to the end of the 15th century, Europe was ruled by feudal lords and nobles. This time is known as the feudal era. At this time, because of the split of the Roman Empire, the landowners acquired the political power in their respective districts, and as a result, they assumed control of the governments of the communities in which they lived. During the time of feudalism, landowners transferred ownership of their properties to members of the aristocracy in exchange for the right to continue cultivating their property (vassals). The term "tax protection" was used to describe this arrangement. This structure gradually got more complicated as more landowners amassed a greater number of vassals. This led to many different degrees of governmental authority, and disagreements amongst landowners sometimes resulted in conflicts that escalated into wars. During this time, the Church was able to exert a significant amount of power politically and had a significant impact on society (Senel, 2017, pp. 237-239).

During this time, the Catholic Church wielded a significant amount of power over the government, and even the Pope had a significant impact on the day-to-day operations of several different kingdoms. Nonetheless, the 14th century was the time when this power struggle encountered its most severe obstacle. In response to the King of France's opposition from the Pope, the King of France took measures to curtail his political influence by capturing the Pope. Following this occurrence, a movement known as the Reformation got its start in Europe. This movement was a response against the political dominance of the Church. The Reformation was a movement that campaigned for greater freedom for people's religious views. This movement was critical of the institutional structure of the Church. This trend resulted in the rise of secularism in Europe and the subsequent decrease of the Church's political influence (Cevizolu, 1999, page 7). Thomas of Aquinas stands out as a significant figure when analyzing the origins of political authority as well as its bounds among the scholars who lived during this time.

CURRENT SCIENCE

The conventional method of conducting political sociology conceptualizes secularization as the diminishment of "religion's social relevance," and it theorizes that this is an inevitable outcome of modernity (Wallis and Bruce, 1992). Because of this, this notion started to come under scrutiny because of the resurgence of religious identities in public and political life in the latter part of the 20th century. On the other hand, the issue of secularism should be treated differently from the perspective of this theory and the predictions it makes. Although it is a byproduct of the Enlightenment and modernity, both of which originated because of early modern Europe's efforts to put an end to religious warfare, secularism is a separate issue from the growth or shrinkage of religiosity in societal settings. A normative political principle known as secularism is one that seeks to respect the freedom of belief held by citizens. In this view, it is a vital component of free and equal citizenship, and hence a necessary step on the way to democratic leadership.

It is a mistake on the part of those who do this to overlook the indifference of normative secularism concerning private religiosity in favor of opposing secularism on the grounds that it is against religion or hampers the freedom of the religious. Those who do this are making a mistake. The goal of secularism is not to endorse or condemn any one religion or set of faiths; rather, it is to protect the freedom of thought, belief, and conscience for all individuals, regardless of whether they identify with a particular religious tradition. Critics are also blind to the fact that allowing hierarchical and absolutist religious groups to occupy political space in the name of freedom of religion is incompatible with a democratic and equitable citizenship regime. This is another point that is missed by critics.

People are given the right to believe in their own free will and to practice their beliefs individually or collectively if they do not infringe on the rights of others. This is because the goal of protecting freedom of conscience and belief, which is recognized by secularism, is not to allow religion or religions to occupy the political arena. Rather, the goal of secularism is to give people the right to believe in their own free will. In a nutshell, secularism is a road to personal freedom and a right that comes with citizenship. If you oppose this and make place for religion and religious groups in the political arena, you will not be contributing to the expansion of current freedoms; rather, you will be contributing to the restriction of such liberties, which will ultimately lead to their destruction. A state does not automatically become autocratic just because its citizens adhere to a secular worldview, even though some authoritarian states assert

CURRENT SCIENCE

that they are secularists. It is difficult to designate a country as secular if the people living there are restricted in their ability to freely practice their religion because of the government's authoritarian policies. A state that does not adhere to secular principles is an authoritarian regime. This is since the governance of such a state is founded, directly or indirectly, on religious principles (as interpreted by the government) and on priorities that are regarded incontestable, as opposed to norms that are negotiated via the use of reason.

secularization

The secularization thesis was an essential part of the modernization theory, which was formulated in the 19th century and served as a compass for the social sciences during most of the 20th century. In the second half of the twentieth century, the forecast that civilizations would inexorably progress towards modernity and, along with it, secularization did not materialize, which led to the formation of postmodernism as a response to this failure. The concept that it would lead to a reduction in religious practice was problematic from the very beginning. This adds to the silliness of the assumption that modernity is inevitable and will develop in the same manner everywhere. For instance, the degree of religiosity in the United States (US), which may be measured by the number of individuals who attend church on a weekly basis, has remained high, even though it has significantly decreased in other European nations. Because of this distinguishing characteristic, several interpretations of what is meant by the term "exceptionalism" in reference to the United States have been up. It has been suggested that individuals' regular church attendance cannot be explained by their religion alone, and this is a viewpoint that may be considered fair. Attending church services was historically regarded as an excellent method for developing communal bonds and fostering a feeling of harmony among individuals. This was the case in cultures that place a high importance on individualism. Because of this, the United States of America may be viewed as an exception, which indicates that the standard rule will continue to be followed.

The secularization thesis, on the other hand, was doomed to fail due to a series of events that transpired in the late 1970s and early 1980s. In a country like the United States, where individual religiosity is already rather prevalent, social groups founded on religious identities have started to organize politically and have gained a large amount of power. [More citation is required] Ronald Reagan was able to win the presidency in 1980 with the assistance of several groups that contributed to his campaign. The United States of America, in its fight against the Soviet dictatorship in Afghanistan, favored cooperating with the Islamic forces in that country

CURRENT SCIENCE

and contributed to the religion-based political mobilization that took place outside of its borders. This was done to defeat the Soviet dictatorship. It is generally agreed that the Islamic Republic of Iran being founded is a far more significant event. In 1979, the Islamists were a component of the wide coalition that was successful in removing the pro-American Shah from power. In addition, there were members of the alliance who held communist and liberal views. After then, the Islamic group was successful in getting rid of the competitors and keeping their grip over the situation. As a direct consequence of this occurrence, every single conventional modernization and secularization thesis was obliterated. The emergence of an Islamic dictatorship was a remarkable outcome for pro-modernist groups that wanted the Shah gone, but it was welcomed by postmodernists such as Michel Foucault. This was a striking result for pro-modernist organizations that wanted the Shah gone. Several modernist organizations advocated for the Shah's removal because they thought he impeded the nation's ability to make social advancements (Afary and Anderson, 2005).

The developments that were transpired in Western Europe provided more evidence that disproved the secularization argument. Since 1980, there has been a discernible rise in the number of persons traveling from nations that practice Islam to those that practice Christianity in Europe. This was one of the results that followed neoliberal globalization took place. The rise in the number of Muslims living in European nations has not only been responsible for reversing the secularization trend that was observed in those countries, but it has also returned the problem of secularism, which had previously been settled, back onto the table. Time will always pass. Once these immigrant groups achieved critical proportions, they began to be identified with their religious identities, whereas before, they were known for their national roots. This was somewhat attributable to the needs of the immigrant populations and partially attributable to the response of the host cultures to the enormous number of culturally assimilable arrivals. The prevalent paradigm of "separation of state and church" was challenged by a growing number of voices, and alternative demands were put up. Postmodernists from the surrounding area were also on board with these alternative demands. There was an increase in the number of people who rejected the model as the Muslim immigrant community in European nations acquired a substantial presence there. They, too, started to have second thoughts about the idea of secularism in the name of "multiculturalism" because they were eager to defend the "right of acknowledgment of the rights of identity groups." This was done to ensure that the "right of identity groups to be recognized" was not violated in any way. Even though it was the

CURRENT SCIENCE

tried-and-true method of maintaining domestic peace after prolonged religious conflicts, the secularization thesis began to fall out of favor when the principle of secularism was put under scrutiny. However, it was the tried-and-true method of maintaining domestic peace after prolonged religious conflicts. As a direct consequence of this, two separate occurrences took occurred at the same time.

The crucial difference between the idea of secularization and the normative principle of secularism can be best understood by considering the seemingly contradictory concept that the purpose of secularism is to protect the religious freedoms of individuals. This idea helps illustrate the difference between the two. A secular state is not the same as a state that is anti-religious; rather, it is a location that defines and creates itself independently of religion and, therefore, affords its citizens the freedom to believe anything they choose to believe. The freedom to believe anything at all, even nothing at all, is an inevitable corollary of the right to believe anything at all. A secular state is a liberal state, which means that it does not interfere with, develop, or impede the views that are held by its residents on an individual or collective basis. This is what is meant by the term "liberal." This is not an ideology; rather, it is a vision of freedom and equality for people, and its goal is to make this happen by neutralizing the role of the state in matters of religion. Secularism is not an ideology; rather, it is a vision of freedom and equality for citizens. A road to the sovereignty of religious groups would be a threat to the freedom of belief that secularism seeks to defend; hence, secularism does not allow religious organizations to participate in the political process. This is for the same reason that secularism does not grant a position in the political arena to religious organizations.

"Everyone has the right to freedom of thought, conscience, and religion; this right includes the freedom to change his religion or belief and the freedom to express his views, either individually or collectively, openly or privately." "Everyone has the right to freedom of thought, conscience, and religion; this right includes the freedom to change his religion or belief and the freedom to express his views, either individually or collectively, openly or privately." This is a fundamental human right that is defined the same manner in both the European Convention on Human Rights and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (Article 18). (Article 9). openly displaying that belief must include the right to not believe anything at all and the freedom not to be obliged to publicly declare this lack of belief to be considered fair. This was made abundantly evident in the very first ruling of the European Court of Human Rights on a breach of Article 9 in the year 2004. (ECHR). In its decision on the case of Kokkinakis v. Greece, the European Court of

CURRENT SCIENCE

Human Rights stated that Article 9 of the Convention was necessary not only for those who belonged to a particular religion, but also for "atheists, agnostics, skeptics, and the indifferent" (ECHR, 14307/88, 25 May 1993, paragraph 31). This was stated in the court's decision on the *Kokkinakis v. Greece* case. The European Court of Human Rights has previously decided that states do not have the authority to compel individuals to reveal their religious beliefs (for example, in the case of *Işık v. Turkey*, 21924/05 of 2 February 2010). This decision was made in previous judgments that the court has handed down.

Hence, secularism may be regarded as a liberal ideal with the objective of defending the liberty of individuals to profess any religion of their choosing or to not believe in anything at all. As a result, it demonstrates that there is a distinct region that is free from the involvement of the state and where people and groups can enjoy their freedom of religion and conscience, if they do not disrupt the public order or infringe the rights of others. It is the obligation of the secular state to establish a political space that is distinct from and independent of religions, and within which all persons may work together to find solutions to their shared issues as members of civil society. Although the number of people who hold religious beliefs may become more widespread or less widespread in a society (depending on whether the secularization theory is accurate), a state can nevertheless adhere to the principle of secularism.

At this juncture, the question that can be asked is whether "freedom of religion and conscience" should include the participation of religion(s) in the political arena, as some postmodernist and multicultural religious groups and their followers, postmodernists and multiculturalists have pointed out. What if the concept of prohibiting the state from interfering with people's freedom of belief went the other way, namely the engagement of faiths and communities of faith in things that affect the state? In this scenario, shouldn't the state, in the spirit of secularism, exert some control over various religious practices?

It is possible to find an answer that is compatible with the question at hand while adhering to the boundaries of normative secularism. It is possible to have political beliefs and preferences based on your faith, and you are allowed to speak to them publicly if you desire to do so. If you do not wish to do so, you should not do so. Your expressing of views that are based on your belief should not be subject to criticism from any other person. Nonetheless, there is a significant restriction that can be inferred from this statement.

Argument

According to Thomas, God is the origin of political authority, and the state is an organization that was established to look out for the interests of its citizens. The goal of this authority, however, is to ensure the well-being of the people; as a result, one of the obligations of this power is to ensure that the rights of the people are safeguarded. Yet, the powers that this power possesses should also be constrained. According to Agaoulları, et al. (2011), these concepts played a significant role in the consolidation of political authority in Medieval Europe in opposition to the Church.

Another blow will have been dealt to the Church because of the emergence of the Reformation movement. At this juncture, the impact that Martin Luther, the founder of Protestantism, had on the development of this movement as well as his responses to the rituals and customs of the Church are of utmost significance. Because of Luther's beliefs, he and his followers became embroiled in a conflict between the authority of the Church and that of the state. Luther believed if the power of the church was restricted, then religion would be practiced more correctly, and Christians would live their lives in a more virtuous manner. The rise of the Protestant movement and the conflict between the Church and governmental authority both received a boost from these ideas when they were given a fresh perspective as a result. This practice has also contributed to the steady strengthening of the concept of separating political and religious forces in Europe (Senel, 2017, pp. 316-319).

XVI. During the 19th century, the changes that have occurred in the West in the social, political, and religious realms have led to new interactions between religion and society or the state. These changes have been brought about as a direct result of globalization. According to Bodin, the sovereignty of the state is based on the unlimited powers of the king, and the powers of the king are accepted as an absolute right that he can use even without the consent of the people. Bodin's theory is supported by the fact that the king's powers are not constrained by any legal constraints. Habbes, on the other hand, had a fundamental aversion to the theories of natural law and social contract. He argued that the existence of the state began with the threatening of people against each other, and he placed an emphasis on the fact that the sovereignty of the state should be protected absolutely. According to Agaoulları and Koker (2009), the theories of these philosophers restructured the relationship between religion and the state and helped pave the way for the development of the contemporary secular state.

CURRENT SCIENCE

The Enlightenment era was responsible for a substantial shift in the ways in which religion and state interacted with one another. The function that religion played in daily life was called into question by philosophers of the Enlightenment, who also held the belief that the part that religion played in politics had to be constrained. The concept that during the Enlightenment, religion ought to be relegated to the field of individual belief, and that the state ought to maintain its neutrality about religious matters, gained broad traction. During this time, the concept that the legislative, executive, and judicial branches of the state should be kept distinct from one another gained traction. This concept emerged contemporaneously with the "separation of powers" notion, which was advanced by philosophers such as Montesquieu. Together with the establishment of this concept, the limiting of the function that religion plays in social life also served to lessen the impact that religion had on the legal system of the state. The establishment of the principle of impartiality in the realm of judicial procedures made it possible to avoid having religion become a factor in the proceedings. The period known as the Enlightenment marks a significant turning point in the history of the evolution of the notion of secularism. According to Hocaolu (2014), on pages 177 and 178, the current notion of a secular state is predicated on restricting the influence of religion in political spheres and defending the right of individuals to believe what they want freely.

The philosophers of the Enlightenment period, particularly John Locke, François Voltaire, and Jean-Jacques Rousseau, were significant contributors to the growth of secular philosophy and the propagation of the concept of separating church and state. Locke maintained that it is the fundamental responsibility of the state to preserve the rights of individuals. He also emphasized the need of maintaining a wall of separation between religion and politics. Voltaire claimed that religion is a private concern and that the state should prefer to remain neutral regarding religion. He did this by battling against religion and church power. On the other hand, Rousseau claimed that the will of the people should be the basis for the state through his idea of the social contract, and he was against the use of religion as a means of establishing political power. These philosophers' views were crucial in the formation of secular philosophy, and they are still widely cited in contemporary conversations on the separation of church and state (Copleston , 1998, pp. 134-136).

The French Revolution is the event that may be the turning point in the formation of secularism. This is because, after all these historical developments and the accumulation of philosophical ideas, the French Revolution was the event that broke the mold for secularism. The French

CURRENT SCIENCE

Revolution was a significant turning point in the emergence of secularism as a political ideology. As soon as the proclamation of the revolution was made, the political authority of the church in France was removed, and it became the goal of the state to establish a framework that was entirely secular. Following the conclusion of the American Revolution in 1791, the United States enacted a Constitution that called for the total separation of matters of religion and those of the state. In addition, measures were implemented, such as the confiscation of church property and the demilitarization of priests and monks. These were both examples of measures that were done. The French Revolution served as a significant model for the current acceptance of secularism and the subsequent adoption of this ideology in other nations. At the time of the French Revolution, church property was nationalized, and members of the clergy were either beheaded or sent into exile. The upheaval that followed the revolution resulted in the consolidation of secularism and the lessening of the role that religion had in both the political and social realms. After the revolution, the "Law of Secularism" was enacted with the intention that the government would refrain from interfering in religious matters and that people would be free to practice any religion they chose (Hazan, 2016, pp. 83-84).

The progression of secularism may be broken down into three distinct stages, according to the secularist historian Jean Bauberot of France. The "pre-secularization period" is the first milestone, and throughout this time, the connection between religion and the state was based on oneness. Currently, there was no separation between the two. The second landmark is the "secularization period," which refers to the time when the state began to disassociate itself from religious authority and develop its own autonomy. The third milestone is referred to as the "restructuring of secularism," and during this time, a new definition and application of secularism came into being. According to Bauberot, each of these thresholds denotes a distinct stage in the evolution of secularism throughout history (Bauberot , 2008, p. 59).

Concepts such as atheism, laicism, and secularization have been brought into the spotlight as a direct result of postmodernism's effect. Others contend that secularism is a product of modernism and requires people to focus entirely on worldly concerns, while others believe that secularism restricts and suppresses people's religious freedom. Some argue that secularism is a product of modernism and requires people to focus entirely on worldly concerns. In addition, because of the process of globalization, the influence of religion in political and social spheres has grown. The line between those who are religious and those who are not got increasingly blurry at the same time as religious people were more involved in politics and had a greater

CURRENT SCIENCE

impact on everyday life. Those who advocate for secularism are quick to condemn the current situation, yet ardent believers in God are on board with the current course of events.

After the French Revolution, there was a very significant period for the development of the idea of secularism. This was since the leaders of the revolutionary movement took a steadfast stance against the Church and made significant progress toward the separation of church and state. However, the hostile attitude and radical measures taken against the Church during this time were criticized for focusing on completely rejecting and destroying religion rather than completely embracing secularism. This criticism was directed at the fact that the emphasis was placed on rejecting and destroying religion. According to Gunn, the time span between 1879 and 1905 is the second most significant time. During this time, significant legislative provisions were established for the institutionalization of the notion of secularism, and the participation of the Church in the affairs of state was restrained. Both developments took place in Europe. But, throughout this time, several flaws and difficulties associated with secularism in practice began to surface (Gunn , 2014, p. 31).

Today, secularism is still a contentious topic that is interpreted and practiced in a variety of ways depending on the nation. In certain nations, the idea of secularism being a fundamental norm has been adopted, while in others, religious ideas are still allowed to have a significant impact on the way the state is run. Relationships between religion and the state have been thrust back into the spotlight in several nations, particularly in the most recent years, and the influence of religious organizations has grown significantly in political spheres. Nonetheless, in certain nations, the idea of secularism is being rethought to accommodate shifting realities throughout the world. In Turkey, for instance, the notion of secularism is understood to mean striking a balance between secularism and religion and maintaining an equal distance from the various religions. On the other side, there are many who hold the view that the notion of secularism is responsible for the suppression of religious life and the restriction of religious liberties, particularly in Western nations. Some opponents argue that secularism should not mean that the state adopts an anti-religious attitude; rather, it should mean that it allows for the free expression and practice of all different kinds of ideas and thinking.

Conclusion

During history, the idea of secularism has been employed in a variety of various contexts and has taken on several distinct interpretations. When the modern concept of secularism is

CURRENT SCIENCE

considered together with its historical progression, both the modern understanding and the evolution of secularism will become clearer.

In earlier times, religious practices and political decisions were inextricably linked to one another. There is evidence that mythological beliefs have played a role in political decision-making and law-making. During this time, intellectual thinkers in Ancient Greece campaigned for the separation of religion and state for the very first time, and conversations also began during this time. By the middle ages, most people in Europe adhered to the Christian religion. The church currently occupies an influential role in both the religious and political spheres. Throughout this time, the relationship between religion and the affairs of state remained to be one of close intertwinement. After emerging from the obscurity of the Middle Ages, the time of the Enlightenment brought about a shift in religion's relationship with the state. During the time known as the Enlightenment, thoughts concerning secularism developed at a rapid pace. The French Revolution is a significant turning point in the history of the emergence of secularism. During this time, which is often referred to as the time when free thinking environments and ideologies in the modern sense began to form because of the French Revolution, the idea of secularism has developed into something that is nearly corporeal in nature. 20, the beginning of what is commonly referred to be the modern period. In the 19th century, the idea of secularism emerged as one of the fundamental tenets upon which modern governments are founded. The administration of the state continues regardless of the religious views of its citizens.

The idea of secularism is practiced in today's world in a variety of distinct ways, depending on the nation. The effect of religion on political life is something that still occurs in certain nations, even though in others the separation of religion and state activities has been made entirely. The idea of secularism is one that is still debated in today's world, and its validity is being called into doubt because of the influence of postmodernism.

Source

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